

The Smart Mouse

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Abstract

I created an inexpensive version of the 'Smart Pulley' that we use at school by recycling unwanted materials.

This affordable version would allow:

- schools which don't have much money to use the best equipment and avoid the use of ticker-timers.
- people at home to experiment with it.
- schools can have a sensor on every or any computer.

I discovered that it was accurate in its measurements and recorded every time the light was blocked and then let through the holes in the wheels. It also recorded every time the magnetic switch was activated.

Materials

- Computer mouse (does not require a track ball)
- Socket and a plug
- A photo gate
- Magnetic reed switch
- Magnets
- QBasic software
- IBM PC compatible computer (an old 486 will do)

Method

Collecting Data

1. Plug the 'Smart Mouse' into the PS2 or COM (serial) port of a computer.
2. Start up QBasic program called 'smouse.bas'.
3. Press F5 to enter settings for the time trial. (Time intervals, length of trials; etc.)
4. Type in the settings that fit your personal needs.
5. Start the trials (eg, roll the trolley or start a pendulum swinging)
6. Save the trials.

Presenting Data

1. Open 'data.txt' in Microsoft Excel. It will come as a list of numbers.
2. Put another list from 0 to 'number of values' (e.g. 12)
3. Drag a box over both columns and click on the chart wizard.
4. Create a velocity vs time graph.
5. Acceleration vs time and Distance vs time graphs can also be made. They are a little more complicated but I will be happy to give you a demonstration.

Results and Discussion

The 'Smart Mouse' that I have created is better than the commercial 'Smart pulley' that we use in school science and physics. Even though the system is still under development I recommend the Smart Mouse for any experiments involving velocity, distance and acceleration. The Smart Mouse is better because it is

Inexpensive: The 'Smart Mouse' is inexpensive and it can be marketed for far less than the commercial 'Smart pulley' system which costs over \$1,000.

Accurate: By using the photo gate, the velocity will be able to be measured to a high accuracy, as opposed to the original wheel blades used to click the mouse button.

Versatile: If the object that you are measuring the speed of moves very fast, you can take off one pair of blades and change the calibrating multiplier. The versatility of the program lets a pulley of a different size to be used in the experiments.

Stable: There is a rubber pad underneath the sensor so that it won't slip during trials.

Fool proof: The mouse button on the mouse is disabled when the Smart Mouse is in use so that the trials won't be activated accidentally.

I would like to continue improving my sensor and use it to carry out experiments for next years Science Fair.

Conclusions

I discovered that my 'Smart Mouse' was accurate in its measurements and recorded every time the photo gate, wheel blade or magnetic switch was activated.

The 'Smart mouse' is inexpensive and it can be marketed for far less than the commercial 'Smart pulley' system which costs over \$1,000.

This simple, inexpensive and reliable device would be a great addition to any engineer's equipment and to any school science department.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank the following people and organisations for their assistance:

NZMP for sponsoring the printing of this poster

Jared Broad from Nexus for the software

Steve Corbitt from the Western Institute of Technology at Taranaki

Andrew Hornblow from Bright Sparks

Michael Fenton, my Research Supervisor

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